

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF TRAUMATIC MARGINAL SUBCONJUNCTIVAL HAEMORRHAGE WITH ACCELERATED HEALING: A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Subconjunctival haemorrhage (SCH) is a common ocular condition characterized by rupture of conjunctival blood vessels leading to extravasation of blood beneath the conjunctiva.^[1] Trauma is one of the major causative factors of Subconjunctival haemorrhage (SCH). Although the condition is generally self-limiting, patients may feel anxious due to sudden redness of the eye. According to Ayurveda, the disease *Arjuna*, one among the *Suklagata Roga* is presented as *Sasarudhiroupama* (reddish spot as blood of rabbit).^[2] The symptoms of both *Arjuna* and subconjunctival haemorrhage appears to be similar. *Pittahara* is the line of management of *Arjuna*. This case report discusses ayurvedic management of subconjunctival haemorrhage with *Kumari Pindi* and *Yastimadhu* and *Lodra Netrapariseka*. *Manjisthadi Kwatha* possesses significant *Raktashodhaka* properties. In that,

Ingredients like *Manjistha* are traditionally indicated in disorders associated with *Rakta Dosha Dushti*. *Kumari*, *Yastimadhu* and *Lodra* being *Chakshushya* and with *Pittasamana* property helped out in complete resolution of subconjunctival haemorrhage within 7 days of *Netrakriyakalpa* i.e. *Pindi* and *Seka* giving significant result.

KEYWORDS: Subconjunctival haemorrhage, SCH, *Arjuna*, Ocular trauma, *Manjisthadi Kwatha*, *Parisheka*, *Kumari Pindi*.

INTRODUCTION

Subconjunctival haemorrhage (SCH) refers to bleeding beneath the bulbar conjunctiva due to rupture of delicate conjunctival capillaries. SCH is usually self-limiting; the sudden appearance of redness causes considerable concern to patients. It commonly characterized as a sharply demarcated marginal red patch in the white portion of the eye (Sclera). SCH may occur secondary to trauma, hypertension, anticoagulant therapy, severe coughing & sneezing, ocular surgery. Traumatic SCH is frequently associated with blunt injury to the eye.

According to Ayurveda, the disease *Arjuna*, one among the *Suklagata Roga* is presented as *Sasarudhiro upama* (reddish spot as blood of rabbit).^[3] The symptoms of both *Arjuna* and subconjunctival haemorrhage appears most similar in feature and characteristics. *Arjuna* is a *Raktha* predominant condition and hence *Pitta* and *Raktha Shamana* is the line of management of *Arjuna*. According to Ayurveda classic *Bhavaprakasha Nighantu* mentioned *Kumari* (Aloe vera) is *Sita*, *Tikta*, *Netrya*, *Rasayana*, *Madhura*, *Bhrimhana*, *Balya*, *Vrishya* and also having *Pittarakta* property.^[4] Also, mentioned by *Bhavaprakasha Nighantu*, *Yastimadhu* is *Hima*, *Swadu*, *Chakshushya*, *Snigdha* and *Pitta* property.^[5] Likewise, according to *Bhavaprakasha Nighantu*, *Lodra* is *Laghu*, *Sita*, *Chakshushya*, *Grahi*, *Kashaya*, *Rakthapittahrit* and *Sophahrit*.^[6] Considering these properties of *Kumari*, *Yastimadhu* and *Lodra*, these drugs were selected for the management of subconjunctival haemorrhage.

In *Ayurveda*, traumatic ocular disorders (*Nayan Abhighata Janya Roga*)^[7] can be correlated with conditions involving *Rakta dushti*, *Pitta prakopa* and localized *Shotha*. Therapeutic modalities which is *Raktasodhaka*, *Sothahara*, *Vedanasthapana* and *Ropana* properties are beneficial in this type of conditions.

In this case report demonstrates the clinical efficacy of Ayurvedic management in traumatic marginal subconjunctival haemorrhage with accelerated healing.

CASE REPORT

PATIENT INFORMATION

A 56-year-old female patient attended the Eye OPD (*Shalaky Tantra OPD*) with complaints of sudden redness in the right eye for the last 10 minutes. The patient gave a history of trauma to the right eye caused accidentally by her own nail.

The patient did not complain of pain, watering, photophobia, diminution of vision, discharge. Only complaints about mild foreign body sensation in right eye.

CLINICAL FINDINGS

GENERAL EXAMINATION

- Conscious and oriented
- Afebrile
- Systemically stable

Systemic Examination

- ☒ CNS – Conscious oriented
- ☒ RS – NVBS
- ☒ CVS – S₁, S₂ Normal, No added sound
- ☒ P/A – Soft & Normal
- ☒ BP – 122/82 mmHg (on 6/4/2026 @11am)

Personal History

- ☒ Bowel- Regular
- ☒ Appetite- Good
- ☒ Micturition- 5-6 times/day
- ☒ Sleep- Sound

Ashtasthana Pareeksha

1. *Nadi* – 76/min
2. *Mutra* – 4-6times/day
3. *Mala* – *Samyaka*
4. *Jihwa*- *Alipta*
5. *Sabda* – *Prakruta*
6. *Sparsha* – *Anushna sheeta*
7. *Druka* – *Raktalochana (Dakshina Netra)*
8. *Akruti*- *Madyama*

OCULAR EXAMINATION (06/04/2026)

TORCH LIGHT EXAMINATION

PARTS	RIGHT EYE	LEFT EYE
LIDS	NORMAL	NORMAL
CONJUNCTIVA	PALPEBRAL CONJUNCTIVA – MILDLY CONGESTED BULBAR CONJUNCTIVA – LOCALIZED SUBCONJUNCTIVAL HAEMORRHAGE IN INFERO-TEMPORAL QUADRANT	PALPEBRAL CONJUNCTIVA – NORMAL BULBAR CONJUNCTIVA – NORMAL
CORNEA	CLEAR AND TRANSPARENT	CLEAR AND TRANSPARENT
PUPIL	NORMAL SIZE, NORMAL REACTION	NORMAL SIZE, NORMAL REACTION
LENS	IMMATURE CATARACT	IMMATURE CATARACT

SLIT LAMP EXAMINATION

Parts	Right Eye	Left Eye
Lids	Normal	Normal
Palpebral conjunctiva	Mild congestion	Normal
Bulbar conjunctiva	Well-defined marginal subconjunctival haemorrhage present in infero-temporal aspect	Normal
Cornea	Clear	Clear
Pupil	Normal size, normal reaction	Normal size, normal reaction
Lens	Immature cataract	Immature cataract

VISUAL ACUITY

- Right Eye (RE): 6/6
- Left Eye (LE): 6/6
- Near vision (B/L): N6

INTRAOCULAR PRESSURE: WITHIN NORMAL LIMITS.

THERAPEUTIC INTERVENTION

The patient was managed with the following Ayurvedic treatment regimen for 7 days:

Sr. No.	Treatment	Dose / Method	Duration
1	<i>Manjisthadi Kwatha</i>	60 ml BID after food	7 days
2	<i>Kumari Pindi</i>	<i>Netrapindi</i>	7 days
3	<i>Yashti and Lodhra Parisheka</i> (3gm each)	<i>Netrapariseka</i> for 200 <i>matrakala</i>	7 days

Netrapindi

Netrapariseka

RESULTS AND FOLLOW-UP

The patient was assessed clinically on Day 1, Day 3, Day 5 and Day 8.

CLINICAL PROGRESS

DAY 1

- Sub conjunctival hemorrhage present +++ at inferotemporal region in sclera
- Chemosis present + inferotemporal region in sclera
- Marginal SCH clearly visible

DAY 3

- Sub conjunctival hemorrhage present +++ inferotemporal region in sclera
- Chemosis present + inferotemporal region in sclera
- No progression of haemorrhage

DAY 5

- Sub conjunctival hemorrhage present ++ inferotemporal region in sclera
- Chemosis + inferotemporal region in sclera
- Marginal haemorrhage resolving gradually.

DAY 8

- Subconjunctival hemorrhage reduced significantly
- Near complete resolution of subconjunctival haemorrhage
- Eye appeared almost normal
- No pain or visual complaints

The patient obtained complete symptomatic relief on 8th day.

OCULAR EXAMINATION (13/04/2026)**TORCH LIGHT EXAMINATION (8TH DAY)**

PARTS	RIGHT EYE	LEFT EYE
LIDS	NORMAL	NORMAL
CONJUNCTIVA	PALPEBRAL CONJUNCTIVA – NORMAL BULBAR CONJUNCTIVA- NORMAL	PALPEBRAL CONJUNCTIVA – NORMAL BULBAR CONJUNCTIVA – NORMAL
CORNEA	CLEAR AND TRANSPARENT	CLEAR AND TRANSPARENT
PUPIL	NORMAL SIZE, NORMAL REACTION	NORMAL SIZE, NORMAL REACTION
LENS	IMMATURE CATARACT	IMMATURE CATARACT

SLIT LAMP EXAMINATION (8TH DAY)

Parts	Right Eye	Left Eye
Lids	Normal	Normal
Palpebral conjunctiva	Normal	Normal
Bulbar conjunctiva	Normal	Normal
Cornea	Clear	Clear
Pupil	Normal size, normal reaction	Normal size, normal reaction
Lens	Immature cataract	Immature cataract

DISCUSSION

Subconjunctival haemorrhage (SCH) occurs due to rupture of fragile conjunctival capillaries leading to blood accumulation beneath the conjunctiva at scleral part. In the present case, trauma by the patient's nail resulted in localized vascular injury causing marginal SCH at inferotemporal region in sclera of right eye.

From an Ayurvedic perspective, traumatic ocular (*Nayan Abhighatajanya Roga*) insult may lead to vitiation of *Rakta* and *Pitta*, resulting in *Ragata* (localized discoloration) and *Sotha* (Congestion). The selected treatment protocol was aimed at *Raktapitta hara* that may be Reduction of inflammation and enhancement of tissue healing.

Manjisthadi Kwatha possesses significant *Raktashodhaka*, anti-inflammatory and healing properties. Ingredients like *Manjishtha* are traditionally indicated in disorders associated with *Rakta dushti* and vascular involvement. *Kumari Pindi* provides local soothing and cooling effects, thereby reducing congestion and localized inflammation.

Yashti (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*) is known for its anti-inflammatory and wound-healing properties, while *Lodhra* (*Symplocos racemosa*) possesses *Shothahara*, *Ropana* hemostatic actions. Their combined use in *Parisheka* helped in reducing conjunctival congestion and accelerated healing.

The progressive improvement observed from Day 3 onwards and complete recovery after 7 days indicate the potential effectiveness of Ayurvedic management in traumatic SCH.

CONCLUSION

The present case demonstrates that Ayurvedic management using *Manjisthadi Kwatha*, *Kumari Pindi* and *Yashti-Lodhra Parisheka* may be effective in the management of traumatic subconjunctival haemorrhage. The treatment showed significant clinical improvement with accelerated healing. Further clinical studies with larger sample sizes are required to establish the therapeutic efficacy of these interventions.

PATIENT CONSENT

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of clinical details and photographs.

DECLARATION OF PATIENT CONSENT

The authors certify that they have obtained appropriate patient consent forms. In the form, the patient has given consent for clinical information and images to be reported in the journal. The patient understands that name and initials will not be published and due efforts will be made to conceal identity.

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Nil.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There are no conflicts of interest.

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